

PROOF OF BEAL CONJECTURE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we give a proof of Beal's conjecture . Since the discovery of the proof of the last theorem of Fermat by Andre Wiles, several questions arise on the conjecture of Beal. By using a very rigorous method we come to the proof. Let $\mathbb{G} = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : \min(x, y, z) \geq 3\}$ $\Omega_n = \{p \in \mathbb{P} : p \mid n, p \nmid z^y - y^z\}$ Let $x = \min(x, y, z)$. The obtained result show that :if $A^x + B^y = C^z$ has a solution and $\Omega_A \neq \emptyset, \forall p \in \Omega_A$,

$$Q(B, C) = \sum_{j=1}^{x-1} \left[\binom{y}{j} B^j - \binom{z}{j} C^j \right]$$

has no solution in $(\frac{\mathbb{Z}}{p^x \mathbb{Z}})^2 \setminus \{(\bar{0}, \bar{0})\}$ Using this result we show that Beal's conjecture is true .

1 INTRODUCTION

Mathematicians have long been intrigued by Pierre Fermat's famous assertion that $A^n + B^n = C^n$ is impossible (as stipulated) and the remark written in the margin of his book that he had a demonstration . This became known as Fermat's Last Theorem despite the lack of a proof. Andrew Wiles proved the relationship in 1994, though everyone agrees that Fermat's proof could not possibly have been the proof discovered by Wiles. Number theorists remain divided when speculating over whether or not Fermat actually had a proof, or whether he was mistaken. This mystery remains unanswered though the prevailing wisdom is that Fermat was mistaken. This conclusion is based on the fact that thousands of mathematicians have cumulatively spent many millions of hours over the past 350 years searching unsuccessfully for such

a proof. It is easy to see that $A^n + B^n = C^n$ then either A, B, and C are co-prime or, if not co-prime that any common factor could be divided out of each term until the equation existed with co-prime bases. (Co-prime is synonymous with pairwise relatively prime and means that in a given set of numbers, no two of the numbers share a common factor.) You could then restate Fermat Last Theorem by saying that $A^n + B^n = C^n$ is impossible with co-prime bases. Beyond Fermat's Last Theorem $A^n + B^n = C^n$ No one suspected that might also be impossible with co-prime bases until a remarkable discovery in 1993 by a Dallas, Texas number theory enthusiast by the name of D. Andrew "Andy" Beal . Andy Beal was working on Fermat Last Theorem when he began to look at similar equations with independent exponents. He constructed several algorithms to generate solution sets but the very nature of the algorithms he was able to construct required a common factor in the bases. He began to suspect that co-prime bases might be impossible and set out to test his hypothesis by computer. Andy Beal and a colleague programmed 15 computers and after thousands of cumulative hours of operation had checked all variable values through 99. Many solutions were found: all had a common factor in the bases. While certainly not conclusive, Andy Beal now had sufficient reason to share his discovery with the world. In the fall of 1994, Andy Beal wrote letters about his work to approximately 50 scholarly mathematics periodicals and number theorists. Among the replies were two considered responses from respected number theorists. Many investigations have been made without success In our paper based on the existing literature (Mauldin, 1997), (Bennet et al, 2014) the Mauldin conjecture (puzzles, n.d.) and the Tijdeman -Zagier conjecture (puzzles, n.d.)], (Waldschmidt, 2004), (Wikipedia, 2018) , we give a rigorous proof to Beal conjecture .

2 PRINCIPLE OF THE PROOF

Let

$$\mathbb{T} = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : x \geq 3, y \geq 3, z \geq 3\}$$

$\forall (x, y, z) \in \mathbb{T}$ consider the function $f_{x,y,z}$ be the function defined as :

$$\begin{array}{ccc} f_{x,y,z} : \mathbb{N}^3 & \rightarrow & \mathbb{Z} \\ (X, Y, Z) & \mapsto & X^x + Y^y - Z^z \end{array}$$

Denote by

$$\mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} = \{(X, Y, Z) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : f_{x,y,z}(X, Y, Z) = 0\}$$

and $\mathbb{U} = \{(X, Y, Z) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : \gcd(X, Y) \geq 2, \gcd(X, Z) \geq 2, \gcd(Y, Z) \geq 2\}$

2.1 LEMMA1

If

$$\bigcup_{(x,y,z) \in \mathbb{T}} \mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} \cap \mathbb{U} \neq \emptyset$$

Then $\exists(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \mathbb{N}^3$ such that $\min(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \leq 2$ and $\mathbb{E}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \cap \mathbb{U} = \emptyset$

2.2 LEMMA 1 PROOF

Suppose that

$$\bigcup_{(x,y,z) \in \mathbb{T}} \mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} \cap \mathbb{U} \neq \emptyset$$

and let $(A_1, A_2, A_3) \in \bigcup_{(x,y,z) \in \mathbb{T}} \mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} \cap \mathbb{U}$ then $\exists(x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{T}$ such that

$$(A_1, A_2, A_3) \in \mathbb{E}^{(x_1, x_2, x_3)} \cap \mathbb{U}$$

So we can find (d_1, d_2, d_3) with $\gcd(d_i, d_j) = 1, \forall i \neq j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $d_i \mid A_i, \forall i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ such that $A_i = \prod_{j=1}^3 d_j^{\theta_j^i}$ Where θ_j^i will be determined by the following relation

$$\prod_{j=1}^3 d_j^{x_1 \theta_j^1} + \prod_{j=1}^3 d_j^{x_2 \theta_j^2} = \prod_{j=1}^3 d_j^{x_3 \theta_j^3}$$

Pulling

$$\theta_1^1 = \frac{\alpha + x_2 x_3 \theta_1}{x_1}, \theta_2^1 = x_3 \theta_2, \theta_3^1 = x_2 \theta_3$$

$$\theta_2^2 = \frac{\beta + x_1 x_3 \theta_2}{x_2}, \theta_1^2 = x_3 \theta_1, \theta_3^2 = x_1 \theta_3$$

$$\theta_3^3 = \frac{\gamma + x_1 x_2 \theta_3}{x_3}, \theta_1^3 = x_2 \theta_1, \theta_2^3 = x_1 \theta_2$$

Let Find $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ such that $x_1 \mid \alpha + x_2 x_3 \theta_1, x_2 \mid \beta + x_1 x_3 \theta_2, x_3 \mid \gamma + x_1 x_2 \theta_3$
Consider the following equation

$$x_2 x_3 \theta_1 \equiv x_1 - \alpha [x_1]$$

$$x_1 x_3 \theta_2 \equiv x_2 - \beta [x_2]$$

$$x_1 x_2 \theta_3 \equiv x_3 - \gamma [x_3]$$

Hence

$$(x_2 x_3)^{\phi(x_1)} \theta_1 \equiv (x_1 - \alpha)(x_2 x_3)^{\phi(x_1)-1} [x_1]$$

$$(x_1x_3)^{\phi(x_2)}\theta_2 \equiv (x_2 - \beta)(x_1x_3)^{\phi(x_2)-1}[x_2]$$

$$(x_1x_2)^{\phi(x_3)}\theta_3 \equiv (x_3 - \gamma)(x_1x_2)^{\phi(x_3)-1}[x_3]$$

Looking for $\alpha < x_1, \beta < x_2, \gamma < x_3$ by the Euler theorem we have :

$$\theta_1 \equiv (x_1 - \alpha)(x_2x_3)^{\phi(x_1)-1}[x_1]$$

$$\theta_2 \equiv (x_2 - \beta)(x_1x_3)^{\phi(x_2)-1}[x_2]$$

$$\theta_3 \equiv (x_3 - \gamma)(x_1x_2)^{\phi(x_3)-1}[x_3]$$

In obvious manner we can assert that $\min(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \leq 2$ if not the process will continue until to obtain this bound By construction

$$\mathbb{E}^{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} = \{(d_1, d_2, d_3) : d_1^\alpha + d_2^\beta = d_3^\gamma\}$$

then

$$\mathbb{E}^{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \cap \mathbb{U} = \emptyset$$

2.3 LEMMA 2

$\mathbb{G} = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : \min(x, y, z) \geq 3\}$ $\Omega_n = \{p \in \mathbb{P} : p \mid n, p \nmid z^y - y^z\}$ Let $x = \min(x, y, z)$. if $A^x + B^y = C^z$ has a solution then if $\Omega_A \neq \emptyset, \forall p \in \Omega_A$

$$Q(B, C) = \sum_{j=1}^{x-1} \left[\binom{y}{j} B^j - \binom{z}{j} C^j \right]$$

has no solution in $(\frac{\mathbb{Z}}{p^x\mathbb{Z}})^2 \setminus \{(\bar{0}, \bar{0})\}$

2.4 PROOF

Suppose that $A^x + B^y = C^z$ has a solution Let $p \in \Omega_A$ Then

$$Q(B, C) = Q(B, \sqrt[x]{A^x + B^y})$$

By the hypothesis we have

$$Q(\bar{B}, \sqrt[x]{\bar{B}^y}) \equiv 0[p^x]$$

Pulling $\bar{B} = \bar{\theta}^z$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{x-1} \left[\binom{y}{j} \bar{\theta}^{zj} - \binom{z}{j} \bar{\theta}^{yj} \right] \equiv 0[p^x]$$

Let

$$\Gamma = \{j \in \{1, 2, \dots, x-1\} : \binom{y}{j} \overline{\theta^{zj}} - \binom{z}{j} \overline{\theta^{yj}} \equiv 0[p^x]\}$$

In the following we are going to prove that $\Gamma^c = \emptyset$. Assume that $\Gamma^c \neq \emptyset$. Then

$$\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \left[\binom{y}{j} \overline{\theta^{zj}} - \binom{z}{j} \overline{\theta^{yj}} \right] \equiv 0[p^x]$$

Let Assume $\theta^z = p^x q + r$, $\theta^y = p^x q' + r'$ and

$$f_n(r, r') = \sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \left[\binom{y}{j} r^j - \binom{z}{j} r'^j \right] - p^x n$$

Assume the existence of the integer root r'_0 and the existence of the integer n_0 such that $\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^j = a_{n_0}$. Where $a_n = np^x + \sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{z}{j} r_0'^j$. Hence $r^{\min(\Gamma^c)} \mid a_{n_0}$. Also we have $a_{n_0} \mid \sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^{j-\min(\Gamma^c)}$ or $a_{n_0} \mid r^{\min(\Gamma^c)}$. Suppose that $a_{n_0} \mid \sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^{j-\min(\Gamma^c)}$ then

$$r^{\min(\Gamma^c)} \leq a_{n_0} \leq \sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^{j-\min(\Gamma^c)}$$

So

$$\frac{r^{\min(\Gamma^c)}}{p^x} \leq n + \frac{\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{z}{j} r_0'^j}{p^x} \leq \frac{\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^{j-\min(\Gamma^c)}}{p^x}$$

which is equivalent to

$$\frac{r^{\min(\Gamma^c)}}{p^x} \leq \frac{\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^j}{p^x} \leq \frac{\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^{j-\min(\Gamma^c)}}{p^x}$$

. Suppose that $a_{n_0} \mid r^{\min(\Gamma^c)}$. Hence $a_{n_0} = r^{\min(\Gamma^c)}$. As

$$\sum_{j \in \Gamma^c} \binom{y}{j} r^j = a_{n_0} \geq 1 + r^{\min(\Gamma^c)}$$

.So $\Gamma^c = \emptyset$. We have now:

$$\forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, x-1\}, \binom{y}{j} r^j - \binom{z}{j} r'^j \equiv 0[p^x]$$

Pulling $R(X) = \binom{y}{j} X^j - \binom{z}{j} X^j$. Since the existence of r'' such that $r'' r' \equiv 1[p^x]$ we have $\forall j, R(rr'') \equiv 0[p^x]$ for $j=1$ we have $rr'' = zy'$ and

$$\forall j, \binom{y}{j} z^j - \binom{z}{j} y^j \equiv 0[p^x]$$

Then $r = z_0, r' = y_0$ where $z \equiv z_0[p^x]$ and $y \equiv y_0[p^x]$. So $\overline{B} = z_0$ and $\overline{C} = y_0$ then $z_0^y \equiv y_0^z[p^x]$. Using this result we have $z^y - y^z \equiv [p^x]$ which is in contradiction with our hypothesis. The Lemma is thus proved.

2.5 LEMMA 3

Let $\mathbb{G} = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : x = \min(x, y, z) \geq 3, y \neq z\}$ if $\mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} \cap \mathbb{U} = \emptyset$ then $\mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} = \emptyset$

LEMMA 3 PROOF

Suppose that $x = \min(x, y, z)$ Then $\Omega_A \neq \emptyset$. Indeed if $\exists p$ such that $y^z - z^y \equiv 0[p]$ then $y^z \equiv z^y[p]$ $z \log_z(y) \equiv y[p]$ and $y \log_y(z) \equiv z[p]$ As $z \neq y$ then $\log_y(z) \in \mathbb{N}, \log_z(y) \in \mathbb{N}$ if $\exists a, b$ such that $z = y^a, y = z^b$ then $z = z^{ab}$ so $y = z$ which is in contradictory with our hypothesis. Hence $\Omega_A \neq \emptyset$ Consider now $p \in \Omega_A$ and suppose that $\mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathbb{E}^{x,y,z} \cap \mathbb{U} = \emptyset$ then Pulling $d_1 = \gcd(A, B), d_2 = \gcd(A, C), d_3 = \gcd(B, C)$ if $\forall i \in \{1, 2, 3\}, d_i \geq 2$ the result will be in contradictory with our hypothesis, so $\exists i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ such that $d_i = 1$ Without loss of generality we can suppose that $d_1 = 1$. Using the relation $A^x = C^z - B^y$ then $d_3 \mid A^x$ so $d_3 = 1$. Using the same idea we have $d_2 = 1$ $C^z - B^y \equiv 0[p]$ As $d_1 = 1$ Now with the fact that $p \nmid C, p \nmid B$ We can write: $C = pk + r$ where $1 \leq r \leq p-1$ and $B = pk' + r', 1 \leq r' \leq p-1, r^z - r'^y \equiv 0[p]$ Hence $\overline{r^z} = \overline{r'^y}$ in $\frac{\mathbb{Z}}{p\mathbb{Z}}$ let $\overline{r'^y} = p - j$ for a certain $j \in [1, p-1]$ Pulling $P(r) = r^y - p + j$ the zero of the polynomial function over the ring $\frac{\mathbb{Z}}{p\mathbb{Z}}$ is $r_k = \sqrt[y]{p-j} \zeta^{\frac{k}{y}}, \forall 0 \leq k \leq y-1$ where $\zeta = e^{2i\pi}$. Using the that r_k is integer then $j = p-1$ and $k = 0$ Beal equation becomes :

$$p^x K^x + \sum_{j=1}^y \binom{y}{j} p^j K'^j = \sum_{j=1}^z \binom{z}{j} p^j K''^j$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{x-1} \binom{y}{j} p^j K'^j \equiv \sum_{j=1}^{x-1} \binom{z}{j} p^j K''^j [p^x]$$

Let

$$Q(X, Y) = \sum_{j=1}^{x-1} \left[\binom{y}{j} X^j - \binom{z}{j} Y^j \right] p^j$$

By the Lemma 2 $Q(A, B) = Q(K', K'') = 0$ has no solution in $(\frac{\mathbb{Z}}{p^x\mathbb{Z}})^2 \setminus \{(\overline{0}, \overline{0})\}$. The Lemma is thus proved

3 THEOREM

Let x, y, z a given integers. Let $(A, B, C) \in \mathbb{N}^3 \setminus \{(0, 0, 0)\}$ such that the Beal's equation

$$A^x + B^y = C^z$$

is satisfied then $\gcd(A, B, C) \geq 2$

3.1 PROOF OF THE THEOREM

Let x, y, z a given integers . Let $(A, B, C) \in \mathbb{N}^3 \setminus \{(0, 0, 0)\}$ such that the Beal's equation

$$A^x + B^y = C^z$$

is satisfied . If $x = y = z$ by Last theorem of Fermat the result yields . Suppose that $y \neq z$ by the Lemma 3 we have :

$$\gcd(A, B) \geq 2, \gcd(B, C) \geq 2, \gcd(A, C) \geq 2$$

then $\gcd(A, B, C) \geq 2$

4 CONCLUSION

In our article gives us a proof of the conjecture of Beal. Our proof is of a very understandable clarity. Although she uses both analytical methods but it is purely arithmetical proof.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author has not declared any conflict of interests.

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